

SUPERSHINE

D5.5 The Utilization of Project Models and Blueprints for Climate City Contracts of the EU City Mission

Authors: Baha Kuban (DEM), Esra Demir (DEM), Buse Araç (DEM), Riccardo Coletta (APRE), Flaminia Rocca (APRE), Paola Zerilli (UoY), Ana Belén Gómez Minguela (CARTIF), Eva Roldan Saso (CIRCE), Isabel Rodriguez (ENA), Cristina Daniel (ENA), Rasmus LT Hedegaard (EGC), Paloma Bozman (ZV), Erdem Çağlar Kocabey (KM), Goran Radulovic (SP)

Technical references

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 CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
BAPV	Building-Applied Photovoltaics
BAS	Building Automation Systems
BREEAM	Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method
CCCs	Climate City Contracts
CIP	Climate Investment Plan
COM	Covenant of Mayors
EBRD	European Bank for Reconstruction and Development
ECAZ	Zaragoza Climate Change, Air Quality and Health Strategy
EIB	European Investment Bank
ePPPs	Extended Public-Private Partnerships
ESCO	Energy Service Company
EU	European Union
GCAP	Green City Action Plan
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning
IETT	İstanbul Elektrik Tramvay ve Tünel İşletmeleri (Istanbul Electric Tramway and Tunnel Authority)
İMM	Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality
İSKI	İstanbul Su ve Kanalizasyon İdaresi Genel Müdürlüğü (Istanbul Water and Sewerage Administration)

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Acronym	Description
KfW	Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau
LEED	Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design
NZEB	Near Zero Energy Building
OSS	One-Stop-Shop
PAESC	Plano de Ação para a Energia Sustentável e o Clima (Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan)
PACCZ	Plan de Acción de Adaptación al Cambio Climático de Zaragoza (Zaragoza Climate Change Adaptation Action Plan)
PMAC	Plano Municipal de Ação Climática (The Municipal Climate Action Plan)
PNEC	Plano Nacional de Energia e Clima (National Energy and Climate Plan)
PV	Photovoltaic
REEF	Riga Energy Efficiency Fund
ROI	Return on Investment
SECAP	Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan
SUMP	Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the Document

The purpose of this document is to present how SUPERSHINE project solutions can support European cities in the development and implementation of Climate City Contracts (CCCs) under the EU Mission “100 Climate Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030”. The deliverable provides a structured overview of existing climate strategies in SUPERSHINE cities and analyses how these strategies can be reinforced through the application of SUPERSHINE solutions.

A particular focus of the document is placed on the development of Blueprints that take into account the diversity of European urban contexts, including differences in governance structures, climatic conditions, and socio-economic realities. In line with the objectives of the project, special attention is given to the affordable energy transition and to the role of public, cooperative, and social housing as key leverage points for achieving climate neutrality in a socially inclusive manner.

By matching city-level actions and targets with SUPERSHINE solutions, the document aims to support cities in translating strategic climate commitments into implementable pathways, while contributing to the overall ambition of enabling 100 climate-neutral cities by 2030.

1.2. Interdependencies with Other WPs and Tasks

This deliverable is closely connected to the overall implementation of the SUPERSHINE project and builds directly on the solutions developed across its different activities. The analysis presented in the document relies on the collective set of SUPERSHINE solutions, which constitute the core input for the Blueprint approach and for the assessment of city climate strategies.

The document reflects the collaborative work carried out with both SUPERSHINE Lighthouse Cities, which act as frontrunners in testing and demonstrating innovative solutions, and SUPERSHINE Follower Cities, which contribute diverse urban contexts and replication perspectives. The assessment of existing Climate City Contracts, SECAPs, and other local climate plans across these cities provides the empirical foundation for the harmonisation exercise presented in the deliverable.

In this sense, the deliverable functions as an integrative element within the project, linking SUPERSHINE solutions with the policy and implementation needs of both Lighthouse and

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Follower Cities. It supports the transfer, adaptation, and replication of solutions across different urban contexts, ensuring coherence between the project's outputs and the practical requirements of Climate City Contracts under the EU Cities Mission.

2. Climate City Contracts in the EU Cities Mission

2.1. Definition and Objectives of CCCs

At a crucial moment in the global response to climate-related emergencies, the EU is committed to lead climate action and has set the targets and legislation to achieve it. Thus, the EU must reduce its emissions by at least 55% by 2030 and achieve climate neutrality by mid-century. In this context, cities have a key role to play, both to accelerate the decarbonisation process and to ensure a fair and equitable transformation that contributes to the well-being of society as a whole.

Despite occupying only about 3% of the Earth's surface, cities generate more than 70% of greenhouse gas emissions and consume more than 65% of global energy. And it is important that they act as hubs of experimentation and innovation in the transition to climate neutrality. The EU Mission "100 Climate Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030" aims to support the transformation of cities to accelerate the implementation of the Paris Agreement, and to be both catalyst and driver for the implementation of the European Green Deal, and a demonstrator that it is possible to achieve climate neutrality by 2050.

In this regard, on November 25th 2021, the Cities Mission launched a call for expression of interest addressed to European cities with more than 50,000 inhabitants interested in participating. Of the 377 that applied, 100 were selected from the EU-27. The original goal was to select 100 cities from across the 27 EU Member States. This was designed to ensure that every country in the Union had at least one "lighthouse" city acting as a testbed for climate neutrality, regardless of their starting point or geographical challenges.

The Mission Implementation Plan foresaw that each of the 100 selected cities would develop a Climate City Contract adapted to its own reality, through a process of co-creation and in close collaboration with the whole of civil society and citizens, detailing the strategy for the deployment and monitoring of innovative and digital solutions to achieve climate neutrality; enabling other cities to follow their example by 2050. This document thus constitutes a clear political commitment, not only towards the European Commission and national, regional and local authorities, but also towards the EU citizens, and includes a comprehensive climate action plan in the different sectors, such as energy, buildings, waste management and transport, together with corresponding investment plans.

To broaden the innovation pool and foster international cooperation, the Commission added 12 extra cities from countries associated with Horizon Europe.

These cities come from non-EU nations that nevertheless participate in EU research frameworks. Examples of these associated cities include:

- Norway: Oslo, Stavanger, and Trondheim
- United Kingdom: Glasgow and Bristol
- Turkey: Istanbul and Izmir
- Other partners: Cities from countries like Iceland, Israel, and the Western Balkans.

Bringing the total number to 112 Mission Cities

2.2. Components of CCCs

The CCC is a process document with three interlinked components. Governance Framework (Commitments), Action Plans, Investment Plans.

Figure 1: CCC Framework

2.2.1. Governance framework

The Climate City Contract (CCC) is a strategic roadmap toward 2030 climate neutrality, developed through a collaborative, multi-level governance process. Led by "Mission Cities," this systemic approach engages public, private, and civic stakeholders to identify and implement the necessary actions for decarbonization. As a digital living document, the CCC is regularly updated to incorporate new investments and lessons learned. Furthermore, receiving the European Commission's "Mission Label" validates the plan's quality, helping cities unlock diverse EU funding and private financing opportunities.

It includes a shared 2030 ambition and a strategy to achieve it, as well as the specific commitment(s) to action from stakeholders in the contract. The document is divided in two parts. Part A covers the 2030 goal, key priorities, principles, and a formal contract signed by all relevant stakeholders. In this first part, the cities identify 3-4 priorities targeting systemic change in high emission sectors. Part B outlines specific commitments from individual.

2.2.2. Action plan and targets

The Action Plan evaluates the efficacy of existing strategies to identify policy gaps and synergies, utilizing diverse "levers of change" to deploy a coordinated portfolio of systemic interventions. It fosters a quadruple-helix collaboration—engaging academia, industry, government, and civil society—to drive the innovation necessary for decarbonization. By building upon current initiatives, the plan defines a cross-sectoral roadmap to 2030. To qualify for the Mission Label, the final Action Plan must strictly adhere to the submission guidelines defined by the European Commission.

2.2.3. Investment and financing dimension

The Investment Plan serves as a comprehensive, long-term financial framework designed to resource the city's transition. It strategically mobilizes public resources, including national and EU-level funding, while establishing mechanisms to attract and de-risk private capital. This financial strategy is intrinsically linked to the Action Plan, ensuring that capital allocation is directly aligned with the city's transformative priorities. Like the Action Plan, the Investment Plan is subject to rigorous European Commission guidelines as part of the Mission Label validation process.

2.3. CCCs in Relation to SECAPs and Other Local Climate Planning Instruments

Sustainable Energy and Climate Adaptation Plans (SECAP's) have been developed by cities committed to the Covenant of Mayors where a SECAP is a strategic document that sets a baseline emission inventory and outlines actions to meet EU targets (typically a 40%–55% reduction by 2030 and neutrality by 2050).

On the other hand, Climate City Contracts is the core requirement for the 112 EU Mission Cities. It does not replace the SECAP but instead, it builds upon it to accelerate the timeline for full climate neutrality from 2030 to 2050. Whereas the key goal of the city SECAP was ~40% emission reductions and adaptation until recently before "Fit to 55" is formulated. , CCC's are targeting full climate neutrality in the same time span, which is 2030. SECAP's contain emission inventories and actions plans whereas CCC's include commitment, action plans and investment plans. The approaches can be said to be more technical and sectoral in SECAP's, on the other hand CCC's are more systemic (over-the-board) and cross-sectoral. Differences in governance also stand out, SECAP's are essentially local government-led where CCC's encompass the whole stakeholder spectrum and multi-level.

For a Mission City, the relationship is typically sequential and additive:

- **Data Inheritance:** The city uses the emission data and risk assessments already established in its SECAP as the starting point for the CCC.
- **The "Upgrade" Path:** Most Mission Cities take the actions listed in their SECAPs and "scale them up." For instance, a SECAP goal to retrofit 10% of buildings might be expanded in the CCC to 50% to meet the 2030 neutrality goal.
- **The Investment Gap:** The CCC introduces a 2030 Climate Neutrality Investment Plan, which specifically identifies how to fund the actions previously outlined in the SECAP, moving the plan from a "wish list" to a bankable strategy.

Legal and political weight is also envisaged to be different and much amplified in the case of the CCC's. While a SECAP is a voluntary commitment with reporting requirements to the Covenant of Mayors, the Climate City Contract is a high-level political commitment. Once a CCC is signed and receives the "Mission Label" from the European Commission, it grants the city easier access to EU funding (like Horizon Europe) and private capital to execute the actions originally envisioned in their SECAPs.

Other forms of Climate Planning have been utilized by global cities but the CoM standard has been adopted by the largest group of cities particularly in Europe.

3. SUPERSHINE Cities Climate Strategies and Matching City Actions to Solutions

3.1 Latvia- Riga

3.1.1 City Profile and Existing Climate Strategies

Riga is one of the selected cities under the EU Cities Mission and has developed its own Climate City Contract (CCC) as the central strategic framework guiding the city towards climate neutrality by 2030. The CCC builds upon Riga's long-standing engagement in local climate planning, notably its earlier Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plans (SECAPs), while significantly expanding both the scope and ambition of climate action to align with the objective of climate neutrality by 2030.

Riga's Climate City Contract establishes an ambitious emission reduction pathway, aiming to achieve a 53% reduction in CO₂ emissions by 2030 compared to 2019 levels, which corresponds to approximately an 80% reduction compared to 1990. A core commitment of the CCC is that municipal infrastructure and operations will reach climate neutrality by 2030, positioning the municipality as a frontrunner and enabler for city-wide transition.

The CCC integrates mitigation actions across six key sectors—municipal infrastructure, energy production, residential buildings, transport, waste and circular economy, and forestry and carbon sequestration—while embedding governance, social innovation, and financing mechanisms to enable implementation.

Municipal Infrastructure and Facilities

Municipal infrastructure constitutes a priority action area within the CCC, accounting for approximately 7% of the total planned CO₂ emission reductions. The strategy for this sector combines energy efficiency improvements with a full transition to renewable energy sources in municipal operations. SUPERSHINE social housing measures, besides the multi-apartment housing sub-sector, will have relevance for this group of buildings. The main targets have been given as;

Key orientations of the CCC in this area include:

- Achieving 100% renewable heat and electricity in municipal buildings by 2030.
- Systematic renovation of municipal buildings, guided by a long-term renovation plan.

- Efficiency upgrades in public lighting infrastructure, including the widespread deployment of LED technologies and full transition to renewable electricity for street lighting, traffic lights and other municipal installations.

These measures are designed not only to reduce emissions but also to generate operational cost savings that can be reinvested into further climate actions, reinforcing the financial sustainability of the transition.

Energy Production and District Heating

Energy production represents one of the most significant leverage points in Riga's CCC, contributing an estimated 37% of the total CO₂ reduction. Given the importance of district heating in Riga's energy system, the CCC places strong emphasis on its decarbonization and modernization.

The main strategic directions include:

- Gradual transition towards fourth-generation district heating, characterized by lower temperatures, higher efficiency and increased integration of renewable energy sources.
- Promotion of zero-emission technologies and renewable energy in heat and electricity generation.
- Digitalization and efficiency improvements in heat generation and system management.
- Development and implementation of innovative pilot projects to test and scale new solutions.
- Increased local renewable electricity generation to meet Riga's energy demand.

In parallel, the CCC promotes electrification and renewable-based solutions in decentralized heating systems and supports connection to the district heating network where technically and economically feasible.

Multi-Apartment Residential Buildings

The residential sector—particularly multi-apartment residential buildings—is addressed in the CCC as a distinct action area, contributing around 2% of the total planned CO₂ reductions. This is also the sub-sector that SUPERSHINE solutions will be best able to match, both in terms of technical solutions but also financial models. While its quantitative contribution is smaller compared to energy production or transport, the CCC recognizes this sector as strategically important due to its links with energy affordability, social inclusion, and quality of life.

The Climate City Contract identifies several enabling actions:

- Improving the availability and quality of energy performance data for multi-apartment buildings.
- Revising legal and regulatory frameworks to remove barriers and accelerate renovation.
- Actively involving residents and housing stakeholders in renovation processes.
- Establishing the Riga Energy Efficiency Fund (REEF) as a dedicated financial instrument.
- Researching and applying standardized renovation solutions to reduce costs and improve scalability.

This approach reflects a shift from isolated renovation projects towards a more systemic and socially inclusive renovation model.

Waste Management and Circular Economy

Riga's CCC also addresses emissions related to waste management and wastewater treatment within a circular economy framework. The strategy aims to reduce emissions while improving material efficiency and data-driven decision-making.

Key actions foreseen include:

- Strengthening waste data systems and infrastructure mapping.
- Waste prevention and improved household waste sorting.
- Expansion of recycling infrastructure.
- Development of a Riga Circular Economy Action Plan for 2026–2030.
- Implementation of an integrated municipal wastewater management plan.
- Public awareness and education activities to support behavioral change.

The implementation of Riga's Climate City Contract is supported by an estimated total investment need of approximately EUR 3.0 billion and is based on a blended financing approach. This approach combines short- and medium-term municipal budget resources with private investment, particularly in the field of building renovation, alongside EU Structural Funds and other EU-level financial instruments, as well as state co-financing and additional financial mechanisms.

3.1.2 Matching Riga City Actions to SUPERSHINE Solutions

The CCC's encompass a wide range of sub-sectors such as the power/heat generation as well as the waste sector which provides ample opportunities for the final GHG emission reductions envisaged by the cities. The report however will only take into consideration the measures potentially undertaken in the built environment which include the following categories;

(P) Municipal infrastructure and facilities
P1: Energy management system improvements
P2: 100% RES heat in municipal buildings
P3: 100% RES electricity in municipal buildings

And

(Dz) Multi-apartment residential buildings
Dz1: Improve availability of EE information and data
Dz2: Revision of laws and regulations
Dz3: Local resident involvement
Dz4: Establishment of (REEF).
Dz5: New standardised solutions for cost reduction.

In Riga, the building sector is the most important component of the city's 2030 climate neutrality goals. With approximately 70% of residents living in Soviet-era housing, the technical and financial feasibility of retrofitting is central to the Riga Climate City Contract (CCC). Riga's strategy is heavily reliant on Citizen Engagement. Unlike many other cities, Riga requires a majority vote from apartment owners to proceed with renovations, making the Return on Investment (ROI) and Payback Period data absolutely critical for convincing homeowners.

Riga's primary hurdle is its high concentration of owner-occupied old apartments, where deep renovation (meaning at least 50% energy savings) must be balanced with strict budget constraints. SUPERSHINE technical solutions align with Riga's CCC priorities as follows:

1. High performance external envelopes addressing massive heat losses in the old apartment buildings; state-of-art glazing and door units, fittings and other cladding. This bundle should address both municipal buildings and multi-apartments residential units
2. Smart monitoring for both DH and internal systems for better balancing and eliminating the overheating/underheating issues
3. Enhanced ventilation post-renovation for improved indoor air quality
4. BIPV and other PV installations to achieve municipal green electricity targets

The SUPERSHINE Guaranteed Savings Model that can best be undertaken by an ESCO entity is a strategic fit for Riga's public buildings and schools, where the municipality expects a guaranteed return on its renovation budgets.

On the other hand, the Shared Savings Model (or the community model) is a better strategic fit for the residential cooperatives, alleviating the psychological barriers for the homeowners regarding the long-term returns. Since the real estate market in Riga is growing robustly, the

SUPERSHINE “property value inclusion” approach is very relevant, not only increasing investor attraction for commercial banks but also resulting in immediate equity gains and lower bills.

Riga specific SUPERSHINE recommendations working towards CCC goals would be;

1. Bundle Neighborhoods: Instead of single buildings, use the SUPERSHINE "District Approach" to lower the cost through economies of scale.
2. Focus on Hydraulic Balancing: Massive energy savings are possible in large residential buildings, at low cost and high ROI. Technical data shows that without balancing the internal heating, energy savings are reduced by 10-15% damaging ROI estimations.

3.2 Denmark- Herning

3.2.1 City Profile and Existing Climate Strategies

Herning has developed a comprehensive and well-structured local climate policy framework aligned with national Danish climate objectives and international standards. While Herning is not a formal EU Cities Mission Climate City Contract (CCC) city, its climate governance architecture—developed under the DK2020 partnership—closely mirrors the logic, scope, and ambition of Climate City Contracts.

Herning’s climate strategies are primarily articulated through two complementary documents:

- the Klimahandleplan for Herning Kommune (Climate Action Plan), adopted in 2022, and
- the Opfølgning 2024 – Klimaplan for Herning Kommune, which provides systematic monitoring and progress assessment of implementation.

Together, these documents form a coherent strategic framework covering emission reduction, energy transition, buildings, mobility, circular economy, land use and governance, supported by regular follow-up and climate accounting.

Herning’s climate policy is based on long-term and interim greenhouse gas reduction targets, aiming for a 50–54% reduction in emissions by 2025, a 70% reduction by 2030, and the achievement of climate neutrality by 2045. These targets are supported by a governance model that requires annual follow-up, biannual climate accounting, and the continuous adjustment of actions. According to the 2024 follow-up report, 70 out of 82 climate actions

are currently under implementation, indicating a high level of operational maturity and strong political commitment.

Energy System Transformation and District Heating

Energy and heat supply constitute a central pillar of Herning's climate strategy. The municipality aims to achieve:

- 100% renewable electricity and heat supply by 2030, and
- at least self-sufficiency in renewable energy by 2050.

Herning operates within a strong district heating framework, which is identified as a key instrument for decarbonizing both municipal and residential buildings. As of 2024, approximately 83% of all dwellings are supplied by district heating, with 88% of collective heat supply already based on renewable energy sources, including biomass, wind and solar energy.

Strategic actions in this area include:

- Expansion of district heating networks in new and existing residential areas.
- Conversion from natural gas to district heating.
- Support for local heat communities in areas not suitable for district heating.
- Development of a strategic energy and heat plan, further strengthened through participation in the LIFE ACT project.

The municipality also actively supports large-scale renewable energy deployment, including wind and solar projects, and innovative spatial planning initiatives such as the “*Energibåndet*” area, combining renewable energy production, nature restoration, and citizen engagement.

Municipal Buildings and Energy Renovation

Municipal buildings play a dual role in Herning's climate strategy—as both a significant energy consumer and a demonstration platform for the energy transition.

Planned and ongoing measures include:

- Continuous energy renovation of municipal buildings
- Improvements to building envelopes and technical installations
- Deployment of rooftop solar PV systems on public buildings

These actions aim to reduce energy consumption, improve operational efficiency, and lower long-term energy costs. Investments in municipal buildings are primarily financed through existing municipal budgets and long-term investment planning, ensuring predictability and financial stability.

Residential Building

A central action area is the expansion and modernization of district heating, which is explicitly framed as a key instrument for decarbonizing residential buildings. The municipality has approved the extension of district heating networks in several residential areas, and the expansion of district heating supply areas is progressing better than expected. Between 2022 and September 2024, the number of dwellings connected to district heating increased by 660, resulting in 83% of all homes in Herning Municipality now being supplied by district heating. Approximately 88% of the energy used in the district heating system comes from renewable energy sources, including biomass, solar, and wind power. For residential areas where district heating is not technically or economically feasible, the climate strategy promotes alternative collective solutions, notably local heat communities (varmefællesskaber). To support this transition, Herning Municipality has established a dedicated funding pool for heat communities, aimed at facilitating the shift away from oil and gas heating systems. These communities are presented as an affordable and socially inclusive alternative to individual heat pumps, particularly in smaller towns and rural settlements.

Waste Management and Circular Economy

Herning's climate strategy integrates circular economy principles, particularly in waste management. The municipality has already achieved 59% recycling of household waste, exceeding national targets for 2025 and approaching the 2030 target of 60%.

Actions focus on:

- Strengthening waste sorting systems
- Piloting innovative solutions such as the EU-supported SorTex project for textile waste
- Expanding recycling infrastructure
- Education and awareness-raising through schools, businesses, and public campaigns

3.2.2. Matching Herning City Actions to SUPERSHINE Solutions

The Herning Climate Strategy (the city does not have a CCC) is deeply integrated with the Danish National Strategy for Sustainable Construction, which mandates some of the world's strictest limits for new and renovated buildings. Herning identifies Municipal buildings in a double role in its climate strategy—as a significant energy consumer and also as a demonstration platform for the energy transition. Herning's strategy moves beyond simple

insulation; it focuses on circularity and intelligent energy management to reach its 2030 goals. Planned and ongoing measures that are part of the Henning decarbonization strategies include:

- Continuous energy renovation of municipal buildings
 - Improvements to building envelopes and technical installations
 - Deployment of rooftop solar PV systems on public buildings
1. Improved external envelopes with better door and window glazing units, high-performance glass utilization, external, roof and floor insulation as well as improved insulation of heat pipes.
 2. Active monitoring via new thermostats, advanced monitoring for all energy systems
 3. Better ventilation

LED fixtures, PV and PV T installations, coming full circle in DH penetration

Regarding SUPERSHINE financial solutions in the housing sector, it is imperative to remember that the Danish social housing sector operates on a highly democratic "tenant-governance" model, where the various solutions are assessed not just on energy efficiency, but on their ability to protect residents from rent increases.

For Herning to achieve its climate targets, the Guaranteed Savings model remains the superior choice for large-scale municipal assets due to its high ROI and investor attraction. Meanwhile, the Shared Savings model is the essential "social lubricant" that ensures the transition is perceived as fair and beneficial by the residents themselves.

3.3 Italy- Trieste

3.3.1 City Profile and Existing Climate Strategies

Trieste has developed a comprehensive Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan (PAESC), formally adopted in 2021 within the framework of the Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy. The PAESC represents the main strategic instrument guiding Trieste's mitigation and adaptation efforts up to 2030 and constitutes the city's primary reference document for local climate action.

While Trieste is not currently a Climate City Contract (CCC) city under the EU Cities Mission, its PAESC follows a structure and ambition level that is largely compatible with CCC logic. The plan integrates greenhouse gas mitigation, climate risk and vulnerability assessment, adaptation measures, governance, and financing considerations within a single, coherent framework.

Trieste's PAESC is grounded in a long-term political commitment to decarbonization and climate resilience. Using 2001 as the baseline year, the municipality commits to:

- At least 40% reduction in CO₂ emissions by 2030,
- with planned actions delivering an estimated 44% reduction compared to the baseline.

Between 2001 and 2019, Trieste had already achieved an approximate 20% reduction in CO₂ emissions, indicating a solid foundation for further action. The PAESC explicitly recognizes that transport, private residential buildings, and tertiary buildings represent the largest emission sources and therefore prioritizes these sectors within the mitigation strategy.

Energy System and Renewable Energy

Energy production and consumption play a central role in Trieste's climate mitigation strategy. The PAESC underlines the currently low penetration of renewable energy sources within the local energy mix, identifying this as a key structural challenge to be addressed. In response, the plan promotes the development of renewable energy production, with a particular focus on solar photovoltaic systems, and supports the deployment of small- and medium-scale renewable installations across both public and private buildings. In parallel, it foresees a gradual reduction in the use of fossil fuels for heating purposes, especially oil-based systems, while encouraging distributed generation and self-consumption models. These renewable energy actions are further reinforced through green public procurement measures and awareness-raising initiatives designed to stimulate market uptake and enhance citizen engagement in clean energy solutions.

Municipal Buildings and Public Infrastructure

Municipal buildings and infrastructure are addressed both as a source of direct emission reductions and as a lever for demonstrating leadership in the energy transition.

Key actions include:

- Energy efficiency retrofitting of municipal buildings
- Upgrading technical installations to improve energy performance
- Reduction of electricity consumption in public lighting and traffic signal systems
- Progressive integration of renewable energy in municipal facilities

Although the quantitative emission reduction contribution of municipal assets is smaller compared to private buildings or transport, these actions are considered strategically important for their visibility, educational value, and role in fostering behavioral change among citizens.

Residential Buildings

Residential buildings represent one of the largest emission reduction potentials identified in Trieste's PAESC. The plan explicitly acknowledges structural barriers related to the city's dense urban fabric, historic buildings, and landscape protection constraints, which limit the speed and scale of deep renovation.

PAESC defines a set of targeted actions for the residential sector:

- Promotion of energy efficiency interventions in private residential buildings.
- Support for building envelope improvements and upgrading of heating systems
- Incentives and guidance for replacing fossil-based heating with more efficient and cleaner solutions.
- Information and advisory activities to increase awareness of energy-saving measures and available incentives.

Actions targeting residential buildings are expected to deliver a significant share of the total emission reductions foreseen by the plan, particularly when combined with national incentive schemes and regulatory frameworks.

Waste Management and Circular Economy

Within the PAESC, waste management is addressed as an integral component of a broader circular economy approach. The plan foresees a set of coordinated actions aimed at improving separate waste collection systems, expanding recycling infrastructure, and progressively reducing the amount of waste sent to landfill. In parallel, awareness-raising and education campaigns are promoted to encourage waste prevention, responsible consumption, and circular practices among citizens and local stakeholders.

3.3.2 Matching Trieste City Actions to SUPERSHINE Solutions

As in Riga, the relevant sub-sectors in the SECAP of Trieste are Municipal and residential buildings;

Municipal buildings and infrastructure, key actions:

- Energy efficiency retrofitting of municipal buildings
- Upgrading technical installations to improve energy performance
- Reduction of electricity consumption in public lighting and traffic signal systems
- Progressive integration of renewable energy in municipal facilities

Energy efficiency interventions in private residential buildings

- Support for building envelope improvements and upgrading of heating systems
- Incentives and guidance for replacing fossil-based heating with more efficient and cleaner solutions.
- Information and advisory activities to increase awareness of energy-saving measures and available incentives.

In Trieste, the building sector is a critical target for the city's 2030 climate targets, particularly given the unique mix of historical Austro-Hungarian architecture and post-war social housing. The Trieste SECAP focuses on neighborhood-scale urban regeneration. The ATER Trieste (Regional Housing Authority) acts as the primary implementation arm for the renovations and modernization which involves a radical "demolition and rebuild" strategy to achieve deep decarbonization. Trieste priorities are centered on high-efficiency residential housing and the transition to a decentralized, renewable-led energy system.

- High performance building envelope via better insulation (external, floor, roof), high performance door and glazing units and facade shading elements
- Energy savings via extensive LED use, active energy monitoring for energy saving behavioral change.
- Renewable heat and electricity in the blocks via high efficiency central heating and building applied photovoltaics, BAPV.

In Trieste, the SUPERSHINE financial models—specifically the Guaranteed Savings and Shared Savings contracts—can be tailored to the city's urgent "dual-mission": deep energy decarbonization and the preservation of the social fabric. Managed primarily through ATER Trieste, these solutions address the functional obsolescence of high-density areas, where low-income and elderly populations face high energy poverty risks. By shifting technical and performance risks to an ESCO, ATER Trieste can undertake radical "demolition and reconstruction" or deep retrofitting without exposing the public budget to underperformance. High ROI makes these projects highly attractive for private investors and green bonds, directly supporting Trieste's goal of reaching carbon neutrality in its residential mission districts by 2030.

While the payback is longer than the guaranteed model, Shared Savings Model is more effective for social housing because it ensures that energy savings are shared directly between the housing provider and the residents. This translates to immediate reductions in utility bills for households. The model serves as a "social lubricant" for urban regeneration, ensuring that the transition low energy buildings is inclusive and does not lead to displacement.

3.4 Portugal- Setúbal

3.4.1 City Profile and Existing Climate Strategies

Setúbal has established a comprehensive local climate governance framework through its Plano Municipal de Ação Climática de Setúbal (PMAC – Setúbal), formally approved in 2024. While Setúbal is not currently a Climate City Contract (CCC) city under the EU Cities Mission, the PMAC follows a structure and logic that is largely aligned with CCC principles, integrating mitigation, adaptation, governance, and monitoring within a single strategic framework.

The PMAC builds on earlier regional and national climate instruments, including the National Energy and Climate Plan (PNEC 2030) and national adaptation strategies, and positions climate action as a core component of municipal policy-making.

Setúbal's Municipal Climate Action Plan (PMAC) is structured around a long-term vision that integrates climate mitigation, climate adaptation, and territorial resilience. The plan explicitly acknowledges the municipality's high vulnerability to climate change impacts, including heatwaves, droughts, coastal erosion, flooding, and sea-level rise, and therefore balances emission reduction objectives with strong adaptation measures. The PMAC is built on three strategic axes; adaptation, mitigation, and governance and knowledge which are further operationalized through seven operational axes covering governance, communication, environmental education, spatial planning, mobility, energy and the circular economy. In total, the plan includes 91 concrete measures, each linked to specific operational axes, implementation responsibilities, and monitoring indicators, demonstrating a high level of operational detail and institutional maturity.

Energy System and Buildings

Energy is identified as a key sector for both mitigation and system transformation in Setúbal's climate strategy. The PMAC promotes a transition towards increased energy efficiency and renewable energy deployment, with a strong emphasis on municipal leadership and integration with spatial planning.

Key actions include:

- Promotion of renewable energy production, particularly solar energy, through deployment on municipal buildings and urban spaces.
- Improvement of energy efficiency in public buildings, including retrofitting measures and optimization of energy use.
- Integration of energy considerations into urban and land-use planning instruments.

Municipal buildings are used as pilot and demonstration sites for energy transition measures, reinforcing the role of the municipality as an enabler and example-setter. While the PMAC does not define a single quantified renewable energy target comparable to CCCs, it clearly aligns with national decarbonization objectives and EU climate goals.

Residential Buildings

Residential buildings are addressed in the PMAC primarily through enabling, regulatory, and awareness-based actions, rather than direct municipal financing. The plan recognizes the residential sector as a critical area for reducing energy consumption, improving thermal comfort, and addressing energy vulnerability.

Actions related to residential buildings include:

- Promotion of energy efficiency measures in housing, particularly in existing building stock.
- Support for renewable energy integration in residential buildings, notably rooftop solar systems.
- Awareness-raising and information campaigns targeted at households to encourage energy-efficient behavior.
- Integration of climate and energy criteria into urban regeneration and rehabilitation programmes.

The PMAC also links residential energy performance with broader social and environmental objectives, including public health, thermal comfort during heatwaves, and reduction of energy poverty. This integrated approach creates relevant entry points for solutions addressing affordability and social inclusion.

Circular Economy and Waste Management

The PMAC embeds circular economy principles as a transversal component of climate action. Waste management is addressed not only as an environmental issue but also as a contributor to emission reduction and resource efficiency.

Actions include:

- Improvement of waste separation and recycling systems.
- Promotion of waste reduction and circular consumption patterns.
- Awareness-raising initiatives targeting citizens, schools, and local organisations.

These measures are aligned with national waste management policies and aim to foster behavioral change alongside infrastructural improvements.

3.4.2 Matching Setubal City Actions to SUPERSHINE Solutions

The Setubal SECAP actions that focus particularly on the built environment (both municipal and residential buildings) are the following:

Energy System and Buildings key actions:

- Promotion of renewable energy production, particularly solar energy, through deployment on municipal buildings and urban spaces.
- Improvement of energy efficiency in public buildings, including retrofitting measures and optimization of energy use.
- Integration of energy considerations into urban and land-use planning instruments.

Residential Buildings key actions:

- Promotion of energy efficiency measures in housing, particularly in existing building stock.
- Support for renewable energy integration in residential buildings, notably rooftop solar systems.
- Awareness-raising and information campaigns targeted at households to encourage energy-efficient behaviour.
- Integration of climate and energy criteria into urban regeneration and rehabilitation programmes.

For Setúbal, the SUPERSHINE approach focuses on transforming social housing districts into smart, zero-carbon neighbourhoods, where technological solutions are specifically tailored to the Mediterranean climate and the Portuguese architectural context. SUPERSHINE analysis for Setubal suggests that the priority should be External Solar Protection. While thermal insulation is standard, the 50% energy saving potential from shading devices is the "low-hanging fruit" for reaching climate neutrality by 2030, particularly in vulnerable social housing districts where residents cannot afford high electricity bills for cooling. SUPERSHINE strategies alignment with Setubal climate targets can be summarized as follows:

1. Passive thermal rehabilitation: enhanced thermal insulation and envelope, targeting up to 30% reduction in heating loads.
2. Cooling and comfort provision: achieved by solar protection and shading, probably the most effective measure in SUPERSHINE Setubal recommendations, cutting off cooling loads by up to 50%.
3. Energy decarbonization: via solar gains by leveraging the massive number of solar hours for passive heating.
4. Energy poverty mitigation: via joinery replacements that eliminates draughts, stabilizes indoor temperatures and is thus a key intervention.

In Setubal, the “cooling” side of the equation is most impactful for overall energy reduction and while individual insulation measures are effective, the SUPERSHINE focus on bundled interventions, i.e. the holistic strategy of treating heating+cooling provides more significant savings.

The SUPERSHINE financial models reveal that Setúbal should pursue a hybrid strategy: immediate, city-wide deployment of Solar Protection (fast ROI, high impact) followed by phased Deep Renovations focused on social housing clusters to capture the high Social Housing ROI. Considering the SUPERSHINE approach with Shared vs. Guaranteed Savings;

for Shared Savings the ESCO maintains a strong 10.13% ROI. This is ideal for Setúbal if the city wants to preserve public capital and let private companies fund the upfront costs. On the other hand, for Guaranteed Savings, if property value is not included, the payback period stretches to 17 years and the Social Housing ROI drops to 5.36%. This highlights a risk: if the real estate market stagnates, the public sector's return on energy alone is much thinner.

To maximize the impact on the built environment while protecting social housing interests in Setubal, SUPERSHINE models recommend the following:

1. Adopt the Shared Savings Model if seeking private ESCO funding, as it offers the highest ESCO ROI (10.13%) to attract bidders.
2. Mandate "All Interventions" (Bundling): This offsets the negative ROI of windows and maximizes energy savings to the 57% mark.
3. Account for Property Appreciation: The 4% ROI "bonus" from property value is the difference between a moderate project and a highly successful urban renewal initiative.

3.5 Spain- Zaragoza

3.5.1 City Profile and Existing Climate Strategies

Zaragoza is one of the Spanish cities selected under the EU Mission “100 Climate Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030” and has formally adopted a CCC as its main strategic framework for achieving climate neutrality by 2030. The Zaragoza CCC is conceived as a political, technical and societal commitment, addressed not only to the European Commission but also to national, regional, and local stakeholders, as well as to citizens and civil society.

The Contract builds on a long-standing local policy trajectory in climate, energy, mobility, and environmental planning, and integrates existing strategies and action plans into a single, coherent roadmap. Rather than replacing previous plans, the CCC consolidates and scales

them, aligning Zaragoza's climate action with the Mission's systemic and transformative approach.

Zaragoza's CCC builds on a comprehensive set of existing local and regional strategies. Key reference documents include the Zaragoza Climate Change, Air Quality and Health Strategy (ECAZ 3.0), the Municipal Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan (SECAP 2030), the Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan (SUMP), the Zaragoza Green Infrastructure Master Plan, and the Zaragoza Climate Change Adaptation Action Plan (PACCZ 2022–2030). These instruments provide the analytical baseline, sectoral targets and implementation experience upon which the CCC is built.

The CCC explicitly recognizes climate neutrality as a city-wide transformation challenge, requiring coordinated action across sectors, levels of government and societal actors. In this sense, the document goes beyond a traditional mitigation plan and positions Zaragoza as a living laboratory for innovation, experimentation, and replication at European level.

The Zaragoza CCC articulates a clear long-term vision of climate neutrality by 2030, grounded in principles of social fairness, inclusiveness, transparency, and co-creation. The transition is framed not only as a technical decarbonization process, but also as an opportunity to improve quality of life, public health, social cohesion, and economic resilience.

A distinctive feature of the Zaragoza CCC is its strong emphasis on multi-level and multi-stakeholder governance. The Contract has been developed through an interdepartmental process within the City Council and with the active involvement of regional and national authorities, research institutions, private sector actors, and civil society. Citizen participation mechanisms, sectoral councils, and open government platforms are identified as key enablers for implementation and social ownership of climate action.

Buildings, Energy and Housing

Buildings and energy systems constitute one of the central pillars of Zaragoza's Climate City Contract, both in terms of climate impact and social relevance. The CCC explicitly identifies the existing residential building stock, including social and rental housing, as a priority intervention area for achieving climate neutrality while addressing energy poverty and housing quality.

According to the Climate Action Plan underpinning the CCC, actions in the buildings and energy sector are expected to deliver one of the largest contributions to the city's overall climate objectives, with a strong focus on renovation, low-emission heat generation, and renewable energy deployment at neighborhood scale.

The Zaragoza CCC sets out a clear ambition for large-scale building renovation, with a particular emphasis on residential buildings. The Contract foresees:

- the renovation of approximately 25,000 dwellings to significantly reduce thermal energy consumption,
- large-scale replacement of fossil fuel–based heating systems in residential buildings, and
- the integration of energy efficiency measures to improve indoor comfort and reduce energy demand.

These actions are closely linked to national and regional renovation programmes, while the municipality plays a coordinating and enabling role through planning, technical support, and targeted municipal aid for housing rehabilitation.

Renaturalisation and Circular Economy

Nature-based solutions and circular economy actions play a prominent role in Zaragoza's CCC, contributing simultaneously to mitigation, adaptation, and social well-being.

Key action areas include:

- Large-scale renaturalisation initiatives, notably *El Bosque de los Zaragozanos*, combining carbon sequestration, biodiversity, and climate adaptation
- Circular economy projects focusing on waste reduction, reuse, and resource recovery
- Integration of green infrastructure into urban regeneration and spatial planning

3.5.2 Matching Zaragoza City Actions to SUPERSHINE Solutions

The Zaragoza CCC sets out a clear ambition for large-scale building renovation, with a particular emphasis on residential buildings committing significant energy efficiency measures and fuel switching in heating. These actions are closely linked to national and regional renovation programmes, while the municipality plays a coordinating and enabling role through planning, technical support, and targeted municipal aid for housing rehabilitation.

Zaragoza City Climate Contract specifically targets the built environment through the following envisaged actions:

- Building renovations
- New Near-Zero Energy Buildings
- Efficient Lighting and Appliances

Low-e heat generation (decarbonisation of heating)

Zaragoza's roadmap to climate neutrality emphasizes a "building structure/fabric-first" approach. The city faces extreme temperature variability—hot, high-radiation summers and cold, windy winters. This philosophy dictates that before investing in expensive mechanical systems like heat pumps or solar panels, the building's permanent structure (its "fabric") must be optimized to minimize energy demand naturally.

The SUPERSHINE technical solutions selected for Zaragoza are justified by three key factors:

1. Combating Solar Gain: With Shading Devices providing a 45% reduction in energy demand and a 2.03°C drop in summer indoor temperatures, this is the single most cost-effective measure to prevent "urban heat island" effects in social housing districts.
2. Sealing the Envelope: Joinery replacement accounts for a 37% reduction. In Zaragoza's older building stock, windows are the primary point of thermal failure. Replacing them is the fastest way to stabilize internal temperatures without increasing the load on the grid.
3. Passive Resilience: By prioritizing Thermal Mass and Cross Ventilation, the SUPERSHINE solutions ensure that buildings remain liveable during potential power outages or extreme heat waves, reducing the "energy poverty" risk for vulnerable tenants.

CCC categories thus find their counterparts in the suggested SUPERSHINE technical solutions:

1. Building renovations: a) replace joinery (37% consumption reduction), primary strategy for reduced air infiltration and winter heat loss, b) Thermal envelope (20% consumption reduction), secondary layer of insulation to stabilize core building temperatures.
2. New NZEB buildings: a) shading devices (45% consumption reduction), eliminate summer loads b) thermal mass (33% reduced consumption), store cool/heat, flattening demand peaks
3. Low emission heating: a) evaporative cooling (36% consumption reduction), alternative to AC cooling b) cross ventilation (25% consumption reduction) natural cooling strategy, cost effective and reduce reliance on mechanical systems.

The SUPERSHINE financial models perfectly support the Zaragoza CCC's focus on residential building clusters. By prioritizing "All interventions," the city achieves its climate goals while maintaining a double-digit return for social housing funds.

Key results for the SUPERSHINE financial analysis that is aligned with the CCC expectations of the city;

- **Social Housing Viability:** The 12.18% ROI for Social Housing in deep renovations is the strongest financial indicator. This suggests that the municipal company, Zaragoza Vivienda, can act as the primary investor, using the high returns to de-risk projects for residents.
- **The Energy Poverty Buffer:** Tenants see a positive ROI (0.64%) even for the least efficient measure (Windows). This is crucial for Zaragoza's commitment to social solidarity, ensuring that renovations don't lead to financial displacement.
- **Efficiency vs. Component-Based Upgrades:** Wall insulation remains the most efficient standalone measure (ROI of 9.23% vs 12-year payback). However, the "All interventions" bundle is the only one that achieves the 50%+ energy saving target necessary for Zaragoza to meet its 2030 Climate Neutrality Label requirements.
- **ESCO Participation:** The ESCO ROI is stable (ranging from 3.5% to 8%). This makes the Supershine models "bankable" for private energy service companies under the Climate Investment Plan (CIP), though they may prefer the 12-year Wall insulation cycle for faster capital turnover.

3.6 Serbia- Belgrade

3.6.1 City Profile and Existing Climate Strategies

Belgrade's climate action framework is primarily structured around its Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan, adopted in 2021 in line with the commitments of the Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy. Through the SECAP, the City of Belgrade commits to reducing CO₂ emissions by at least 40% by 2030 compared to 2015, increasing resilience to climate impacts, and ensuring access to sustainable and affordable energy for its population.

The SECAP represents the first comprehensive, city-wide climate strategy for Belgrade and is closely coordinated with the city's Green City Action Plan (GCAP) developed under the EBRD Green Cities Framework. Together, these documents provide a structured baseline, strategic objectives, and a detailed action portfolio covering mitigation, adaptation, and resilience. Buildings, energy systems, transport, and district heating emerge as priority sectors, reflecting Belgrade's emissions profile and socio-economic context.

The Baseline Emission Inventory highlights a highly concentrated emissions profile, with buildings accounting for approximately 79% of total CO₂ emissions, and residential buildings

alone contributing around 68%. This context strongly shapes the action priorities defined in the SECAP.

Residential Buildings

Residential buildings constitute the most critical intervention area within Belgrade's climate strategy. The SECAP identifies inefficient building envelopes, outdated heating systems, and high reliance on electricity and fossil fuels for space heating as key challenges.

To respond to these challenges, the SECAP defines a set of actions focusing on improving the energy performance of the existing residential building stock. These actions emphasize renovation and efficiency upgrades beyond minimum national requirements, supported by regulatory and incentive-based approaches. In particular, the plan foresees:

- large-scale energy efficiency improvements in existing residential buildings,
- promotion of building renovation beyond minimum national standards,
- encouragement of façade insulation, window replacement, and roof improvements,
- facilitation of the integration of renewable energy sources in residential buildings where technically feasible, and
- awareness-raising and capacity-building activities aimed at homeowners and housing associations.

Municipal Buildings and Public Infrastructure

Municipal buildings are addressed in the SECAP both as an operational priority and as a means of demonstrating best practices. The plan recognizes the importance of leading by example, particularly in a context where large-scale residential renovation requires increased public trust and awareness.

Actions in this area focus on improving the energy performance of public assets through:

- energy refurbishment of municipal buildings,
- upgrading of heating and cooling systems,
- implementation of energy management measures, and
- deployment of renewable energy systems on public buildings.

These interventions are expected to generate operational savings for the municipality while providing replicable models for other building owners.

District Heating and Energy Systems

Decarbonization of heating is a cornerstone of Belgrade's climate strategy. The SECAP identifies district heating as a key structural solution for reducing emissions, improving air

quality, and increasing affordability in dense urban areas. The expansion and modernization of the district heating system is therefore treated as a strategic priority rather than a standalone infrastructure project. The plan outlines a comprehensive action package aimed at strengthening the district heating system.

- rehabilitation and efficiency improvements of heat production facilities,
- reduction of heat losses across the distribution network,
- expansion of the district heating network to connect approximately 97,000 additional customers by 2030, and
- gradual integration of lower-carbon and renewable energy sources into heat production.

Waste Management, Circular Economy, and Environmental Actions

Beyond buildings and energy systems, Belgrade's SECAP also addresses environmental pressures related to waste management, resource efficiency, and urban environmental quality. These actions are framed as supporting measures that contribute to emission reduction, climate resilience, and improved living conditions, rather than as a standalone circular economy strategy. Actions in this area focus on strengthening the waste management system and gradually introducing circular economy principles improvement and expansion of separate waste collection, particularly for recyclable fractions,

- reduction of waste sent to landfill through increased recycling and recovery,
- upgrading of waste management infrastructure, and
- promotion of waste prevention and environmentally responsible behaviour among citizens.

The implementation of Belgrade's SECAP is supported by a clearly defined investment framework that reflects the scale of transformation required in the buildings and energy sectors. For the period 2021–2030, the total capital expenditure is estimated at approximately EUR 5.16 billion. The plan is based on a mixed financing model that combines municipal resources, including investments by municipally owned utilities, with private investment, particularly in residential buildings and energy infrastructure, as well as external public financing from international financial institutions and donors. Approximately 73% of the total investment is allocated to mitigation actions, with a substantial share directed towards buildings and district heating. In this context, the SECAP foresees the use of public–private partnerships and financing instruments from institutions such as the EBRD, EIB, and KfW to support effective implementation.

3.6.2 Matching Belgrade City Actions to SUPERSHINE Solutions

The Belgrade SECAP of March 2021 clearly identifies efficiency and improvement in the district heating system in the Energy and Efficiency main category as the following priority actions;

- E1 - Connecting to the natural gas distribution network
- LE1 - Development and improvement of the district heating distribution network
- LE2 - Improvement energy efficiency district heating heat sources

The next outstanding actions listed are efficiency and automation of the public lighting system. Regarding those topics of interest for SUPERSHINE solutions is the emphasis on energy efficiency in both municipal and residential buildings:

- B1 - Renovation / Energy efficiency and use of RES in municipal buildings
- B3 - Energy efficiency and use of RES in residential buildings
- B4 - Regulations and incentive measures in residential buildings

As the building sector in Belgrade is the primary source of carbon emissions, accounting for approximately 79% of the city's total footprint, SUPERSHINE Technical and Financial Solutions are designed to address this by targeting residential clusters, particularly socialist-era multi-family buildings that currently suffer from high energy loss. SUPERSHINE analysis of Belgrade data reveals that the city's climate requires as dual-forked strategy due to hot summer and cold winters.

1. Shading Devices

- Energy Impact: -42% consumption reduction (highest points)
- Comfort Impact: -2.13°C operative temperature.
- Strategic Value: For Belgrade's massive multi-family blocks (like those in New Belgrade), external shading is the most effective way to combat the "urban heat island" effect. It prevents the need for massive air-conditioning expansion, which currently threatens the city's electricity grid stability in summer.

2. Retrofitting the Socialist-Era Building Envelope

- Thermal Envelope: Combined heating and cooling strategies result in a -34% reduction in energy consumption.
- Joinery (Windows): Replacing outdated socialist-era joinery leads to a -29% consumption reduction and a significant +0.86°C increase in winter operative temperature.

- Insight: Since 61% of energy consumption in Belgrade comes from the residential sector, focusing on the "Thermal Envelope" bundle is the most efficient path to the city's 40% emission reduction target.

3. Evaporative Cooling Potential

- Consumption Reduction: -40%

The data supports recent research suggesting that Belgrade's climate is highly suitable for evaporative systems, which provide a low-energy alternative to traditional vapor-compression AC.

The SUPERSHINE technical analysis and solutions indicate that while heating retrofits are standard, the "Cooling Passive Strategies" (specifically Shading and Evaporative systems) offer the highest percentage of energy savings for Belgrade and integrating these into the Belgrade renovation effort will be essential for meeting the 2030 Climate Neutrality targets.

The financial data for Belgrade (Serbia) offers a clear look at how market dynamics—specifically property value appreciation and contracting types—dictate the feasibility of the city's renovation efforts. For Belgrade, including property value is not just an accounting preference; it is a necessity. Without it, the payback period for deep renovation jumps from 13 to 17 years, and the ROI for the public sector (Social Housing) nearly halves (dropping from ~11% to ~6%). This confirms that Belgrade's retrofitting strategy must be marketed as **Urban Regeneration**, not just energy saving.

SUPERSHINE financial solutions, in concert with the results constructed by the technical analysis leads to the following strategy for Belgrade to achieve its 40% emission reduction target by 2030;

1. Prioritize Guaranteed Savings Contracts to maximize the ROI for municipal housing funds.
2. Bundle Interventions: The 58.5% energy saving from the bundle is twice as effective as wall insulation alone (33%).
3. Formalize Property Value Gains: Integrate real estate appraisal into energy audits to unlock the faster 13-year payback cycle.

3.7 Türkiye- Istanbul

3.7.1 City Profile and Existing Climate Strategies

Istanbul's main climate strategy document for the EU Cities Mission is its Climate City Contract, which is structured around a 2030 Climate Neutrality Action Plan. The CCC sets

out a citywide pathway to reach climate neutrality by 2030, primarily by achieving a large emissions reduction by 2030 and addressing any remaining balance through complementary approaches.

A key strength of Istanbul's CCC is that it translates ambition into an action portfolio: the plan includes 28 actions grouped under eight focus areas (Built environment; Energy systems; Green infrastructure & nature-based solutions; Mobility & transport; Waste & circular economy; Water management; Agriculture & food; Sinks & compensation).

Built environment: municipal assets and housing-oriented actions

The CCC gives notable weight to buildings and the housing agenda, combining municipal retrofits with a climate-resilient, social-housing-oriented pilot.

Action 1 (Net zero buildings – IMM administrative buildings): Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality (IMM) proposes a package of energy efficiency measures for 19 administrative buildings of IMM and affiliates (e.g., IETT, ISKI, ISTAC, Metro Istanbul), covering a broad retrofit set such as:

- thermal insulation,
- LED transformation,
- building automation systems (BAS),
- replacement/optimization of pumps, motors and HVAC,
- energy monitoring systems and ISO 50001 alignment,
- energy audits and industrial/process efficiency measures where relevant.

The CCC also provides an indicative total cost for this action (EUR 51.5 million).

Action 2 (Net zero buildings – NZEB temporary social housing units): This is one of the clearest “housing” anchors in the CCC, framed at the intersection of earthquake risk / urban transformation and energy performance. The CCC notes that Istanbul has a large stock of high-risk buildings. The action is designed as a pilot to demonstrate “green building” benefits while meeting the need for temporary housing during transformation processes.

What makes this particularly relevant for public/social housing and replicable “blueprints” is that the CCC defines a performance-and-quality envelope for the housing units. The units are expected to be, among others:

- seismically robust and energy efficient (at nZEB rates),
- resource-, water- and carbon-efficient,
- climate/extreme-weather resilient and smart/easy to operate,
- livable and socially enriching, mixed-use (with facilities and commercial areas),
- accessible and inclusive, with high indoor environmental quality,

- prioritizing renewables and being fossil-free, and “ready” for future integration to district heating systems,
- aligned with relevant certification criteria (YeS-TR, B.E.S.T. Konut, LEED, BREEAM, WELL, etc.).

The CCC places strong emphasis on pilot and demonstration projects that can inform future large-scale renovation and housing programmes. A flagship example is the Build4GreenIstanbul (BUILD4GREENIST) project, which is referenced in the CCC as a testbed for integrated, low-carbon building solutions. The project focuses on the deep renovation and transformation of existing residential buildings, combining energy efficiency, renewable energy integration, and digital solutions.

Taken together, Actions 1–2 show Istanbul’s dual approach: (i) reduce energy demand and modernize municipal assets, and (ii) use a pilot NZEB social/temporary housing model as a demonstrator that integrates resilience, inclusion, and operational practicality.

Energy systems: a grid-mix objective

In energy systems, the CCC combines municipal operational actions with a broader target on electricity supply.

Action 8 (Increasing renewable electricity – 71% renewables by 2030): The CCC includes a citywide electricity-mix goal: 71% renewable electricity by 2030, noting that complementary actions (e.g., local generation actions) will contribute, but also emphasizing that national-level policies will be decisive to achieve the target.

Waste and circular economy: food waste, biomethanisation, and collection efficiency

The CCC includes a coherent mini-package around organic waste and system efficiency—useful for matching to circular economy and bioenergy solutions.

Action 23 (Food & yard waste recycling – reduce/avoid discarded food): The CCC describes Istanbul’s governance structure for waste (district municipalities collect; IMM disposes) and explains why food waste tends to remain mixed in municipal waste: rapid decomposition, costly processing, and low secondary revenue make it unattractive for recyclers. It notes IMM already collects food waste from commercial sources (hotels, restaurants, ready-meal companies, weekly street markets) through mutual agreements and seeks to extend and streamline this operation to reduce operating costs. Indicative total cost is provided (EUR 68.0 million).

Action 24 (Biomethanisation plants): The CCC frames this as a scale issue (noting 17,600 tons/day of solid waste reaching disposal facilities) and stresses the need for preventing organic waste from mixing/contaminating other waste streams to run biomethanisation efficiently. Where separation at source is weak, the CCC points to mechanical separation as pre-treatment for biomethane plants. It states IMM is willing to increase existing biomethanisation capacity and proposes implementing current plans, with an indicative total cost of EUR 59.0 million.

3.7.2 Matching City Actions to SUPERSHINE Solutions

SUPERSHINE analysis of Istanbul data presents a unique and critical challenge within the Project's framework. As a Fellow City, Istanbul's transition is defined by the dual imperative of Climate Neutrality by 2030 and Seismic Resilience. Because Istanbul sits on major fault lines, "Deep Renovation" here is not just an energy efficiency measure—it is a matter of life safety. The Istanbul Climate City Contract (CCC) specifically highlights that 64% of the city's emissions come from stationary energy (buildings), making this sector the most significant lever for change. In a strategic alignment, SUPERSHINE outcomes need to line up with the CCC targets:

1. Seismic and Green Synergy: Structural + Thermal retrofit where SUPERSHINE "Renovation Kits" must integrate structural reinforcement with insulation to address the primary survival concern of residents
2. Public sector leadership: The municipality aims for 100% green energy in municipal buildings and SUPERSHINE provides the ROI framework for rooftop solar.
3. Just transition via mitigation of energy poverty: Ensuring "Green Transformation" does not lead to financial displacement of vulnerable households.

In Istanbul, passive strategies must be viewed through a "Seismic + Energy" lens. The city cannot afford to renovate buildings twice.

- Envelope Modernization: Replacing heavyweight, uninsulated masonry with lightweight, high-performance thermal materials that reduce the "dead load" on building structures—enhancing both earthquake safety and energy retention.
- Active Systems: All new or majorly renovated buildings over 2,000 must now meet Near Zero Energy Building (NZEB) standards, requiring at least 10% renewable energy contribution.
- Cooling & Heat Island Mitigation: As a city facing significant "Urban Heat Island" effects, passive cooling (shading and reflective surfaces) is prioritized to reduce summer peak electricity demand.

SUPERSHINE technical analysis brings into relief the key intervention points:

1. Solar Protection (Shading)

- Consumption Reduction: -39%
- Operative Temperature Change: -1.82°C
- Notes: In dense districts like Kadıköy, solar protection is the most cost-effective way to achieve CCC's cooling targets. It prevents "AC-overload" during heatwaves, which is a major concern for the local grid stability.

2. Window Performance & Thermal Comfort

- Consumption Reduction: -17%
- Comfort Impact: +0.96°C (Operative Temperature)
- Notes: While the consumption reduction for windows is lower than shading, the +0.96°C increase in winter operative temperature is a high "comfort boost" according to SUPERSHINE analysis. This would be vital for addressing energy poverty in Kadıköy's aging social housing stock.

3. The "Thermal Envelope" Bundle

- Consumption Reduction: -38%
- Notes: The total envelope approach (Walls + Roof + Windows) matches the impact of standalone shading. This suggests that in Istanbul, a deep renovation must include high-performance shading to be truly effective.

As of 2026, the Build4GreenIST project just completed, is promoting the strategy of creating a "Transition Guide to Green and Carbon Neutral Buildings." The high performance of shading and ventilation in SUPERSHINE analysis supports this push for "Passive-First" designs in urban transformation zones.

The financial analysis for Kadıköy reveals that the intersection of real estate value and energy savings is the most critical driver for large-scale transformation in Turkey.

In Istanbul, including the increase in property market value can be seen to be a game-changer.

- It reduces the payback period by 4 years (from 17 to 13).
- Under the Guaranteed Savings model, it boosts the Social Housing ROI from 6.16% to 9.77%.
- This aligns with local market data showing that energy-efficient homes in Istanbul command an 8.1% price premium over standard properties.

Considering these key findings:

The SUPERSHINE financial model for Istanbul identifies the Guaranteed Savings Contract (with Property Value) as the optimal tool for the 2030 mission.

- For the Municipality (Social Housing): Achieves a nearly double-digit ROI (9.77%), making it easier to secure green bonds or international climate finance.
- For the Private Sector (ESCO): Offers a robust 8.22% ROI, sufficient to attract investment for instance in the "Hasanpaşa Residential Properties" and beyond.
- For the People (Tenants): A 5.01% ROI ensures that the "Green Transformation" remains socially just and affordable for vulnerable citizens.

4. Conclusion

The SUPERSHINE project demonstrates that achieving 2030 climate neutrality in the building sector is technically feasible but financially complex. The core lesson is that buildings are not isolated units; they are nodes in a district-level energy ecosystem. To meet the EU's targets for the built environment, cities must transition from building-by-building retrofits to integrated Smart Neighbourhood transformations.

City specific success factors come out as:

Resilience in Istanbul, with a dual retrofit model that incorporates seismic+energy renovations, Social Justice in Trieste and Herring, prioritizing deep renovation (60%+ savings) in social housing without tenant displacement, Efficiency in Belgrade and Riga, Modernizing district heating (DH) as the single fastest lever for mass decarbonization as well as energy saving retrofits and finally Adaptation in Zaragoza and Setubal, focusing on cooling passive strategies for the highest gains.

The SUPERSHINE technical and financial analyses carried out across diverse European countries and cities reveal a clear set of strengths and weaknesses. From a technical perspective, a consistent finding is the cost-effectiveness of a “passive-first” approach. Across all case cities, passive solar protection measures and high-performance building envelopes proved more efficient than relying solely on active, high-tech system replacements. In particular, shading strategies and natural ventilation—especially relevant in Southern European contexts—reduced cooling loads by up to 39%, helping to avoid electricity grid stress caused by increased air-conditioning demand. However, a notable weakness remains in historical masonry buildings, such as those in Trieste and Riga, where heritage protection constraints limit the use of external insulation. This creates an innovation gap that often requires more complex and costly internal insulation or advanced technological solutions.

From a financial perspective, the SUPERSHINE experience highlights the critical importance of incorporating property market value into renovation business models. Including value appreciation significantly improves project feasibility, reducing payback periods by an average of four to six years and making renovation projects more attractive and bankable for private ESCOs. Nevertheless, a persistent EU funding deficit in the social housing sector remains a major barrier. In cities such as Belgrade and Riga, fragmented ownership structures in multi-apartment buildings frequently lead to decision-making paralysis, a challenge that cannot be resolved by public grants alone.

To bridge this funding gap and remain on track for the 2030 climate targets, cities need to increasingly adopt Extended Public-Private Partnerships (ePPPs) and One-Stop-Shop

(OSS) models. For municipal and social housing, Guaranteed Savings Contracts—where the ESCO assumes performance risk—emerge as the most robust financial instrument. These contracts provide the predictability required by commercial banks and enable municipalities to use limited EU public funds as leverage to mobilise substantially larger volumes of private capital. In parallel, project aggregation at the district or neighborhood scale is essential. Individual buildings are often too small to attract institutional investors, whereas bundling multiple projects can reduce overall costs by 15–20% through economies of scale.

Addressing energy poverty is a central component of this transition. For social housing, Shared Savings models should become the default approach, ensuring that tenants benefit from energy cost reductions immediately after renovation. This mechanism supports a just transition by preventing energy efficiency investments from triggering “green gentrification” and displacement of low-income households.

Overall, the SUPERSHINE experience demonstrates that technical solutions are already available; however, achieving the 2030 goals will require cities to treat energy efficiency as a form of public infrastructure rather than a purely private real-estate decision. Fellow cities are encouraged to replicate One-Stop-Shop models to reduce technical and administrative barriers for residents, while at EU level, the establishment of a dedicated Social Housing Renovation Fund is strongly recommended to de-risk ESCO investments in low-income districts and accelerate large-scale renovation efforts.

References

Câmara Municipal de Setúbal. (2024). *Plano Municipal de Ação Climática – Setúbal* [Municipal climate action plan].

City of Belgrade. (2021). *Sustainable energy and climate action plan for the City of Belgrade*.

Comune di Trieste. (2021). *Piano d'azione per l'energia sostenibile e il clima (PAESC) del Comune di Trieste*.

Herning Kommune. (2022). *Klimahandleplan for Herning Kommune* [Climate action plan for Herning Municipality].

Herning Kommune. (2024). *Opfølgning 2024: Klimaplan for Herning Kommune* [Annual follow-up report].

Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality. (2023). *2030 climate neutrality action plan of the City of Istanbul: Climate City Contract*. NetZeroCities Programme (EU Mission: Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities).

NetZeroCities. (n.d.). *Climate City Contract: Quick read*. <https://netzerocities.app/QR-CCC>

Riga State City Municipality. (2023). *2030 climate-neutrality action plan of Riga State City: Climate City Contract*. NetZeroCities Programme

Zaragoza City Council. (2022). *Zaragoza Climate City Contract*. NetZeroCities Programme (EU Mission: 100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities)

